

SELF-CONTAINED TOOLING FOR CURING OF
INTEGRALLY STIFFENED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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Viabile manufacturing tooling options are needed which provide for rapid tool cycling, freedom of production scheduling, and significant energy conservation with overall program cost advantages. A method has been developed and demonstrated which provides all of the cure environment such as vacuum, high pressure, and heating for curing of advanced composites that traditionally have been provided by autoclave facilities.

The self-contained tooling concept utilizes a pneumatic diaphragm for pressure application, electric heater blankets and expansion bars, and cast ceramic dies which provide contour control and thermal insulation. A single force cage is used with interchangeable tooling inserts to precure composite details and then bond these details into an integrally stiffened structure.

Use of the pneumatic diaphragm provides a very simple method for controlling potential tooling over pressurization commonly associated with thermally expanding rubber tools, while maintaining the advantages of the rubber system. Selective heating of pressure bars and heating blankets assures the proper sequencing of temperature and pressure events critical to consolidation of organic matrix based composites.

Tooling cost comparisons were made with a family of autoclave tools that would be required to perform the same processing operations. Energy measurements were taken which demonstrated substantial energy savings using the self-contained tooling approach.